

TES Cluster

Thermal Energy Storage

Find out more!

ECHO: Efficient compact modular thermal energy storage system

The EU-funded **ECHO** project plans to develop an alternative **thermal energy storage solution**. The proposed system will be compact, flexible, modular, plug-and-play, sustainable and digitally controlled. It will be based on **thermochemical materials** combined with phase change materials for space heating and cooling, domestic hot water production and ice storage. The system will be charged either by exploiting the electricity overproduction from the grid or by directly connecting to renewable energy sources installed in the building.

THUMBS UP: Thermal energy storage solutions to optimally Manage Buildings and Unlock their grid balancing and flexibility Potential

The EU funded **THUMBS UP** project will develop and demonstrate daily and weekly TES for **EU buildings**. By innovating at different levels, from modelling to materials and enhancing heat exchanger solutions, the project will design high-performance **TES solutions** in line with EU sustainable economy goals. The project will set up **three demo sites in Spain and Sweden** – in different EU climates and energy market contexts. hot water production and ice storage.

HYSTORE: Hybrid services from advanced thermal energy storage systems

The EU-funded **HYSTORE** project will advance **TES technology** by combining different innovative components. The project aims to achieve up to 150 % energy density and 50 % lower capital expenditures compared to the state-of-the-art TES systems. The project will cover four different use cases in various **climates and environments**, for district heating/cooling connected and non-connected buildings.

BEST-STORAGE: Building energy efficient system through short and long spectrum thermal energy storage

The EU-funded **BEST-Storage** project will develop both long- and short term high-energy density storage solutions. These include a **thermo-chemical and loss-free storage technology** for seasonal storage, and two phase-change materials slurry concepts and vacuum-insulated water storage, for cold and warm applications, respectively, to shift peak load demands. The project will integrate these storage solutions into **smart-building energy management systems** to **reduce operating costs for short-term applications**.

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